

On a sigmoid-based model for quantum correlations in the EPR paradox

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A theoretical and numerical analysis of a Bell-type experiment is presented, where measurements are modeled using a threshold mechanism based on a sigmoid function that exploits the detection loophole and violates the fair sampling assumption. The experimental setup measures correlations between linear polarization of entangled photons, prepared in non-maximally entangled states. The numerical simulation shows the model's limitations with respect to quantum mechanical theoretical predictions, demonstrates that this mechanism leads to violation of Bell's inequality, and could provide insights into the nature of spooky measurements at a distance.

I. Introduction

The Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen paradox [1] and Bell's subsequent theorem [2] established a fundamental incompatibility between locality and the completeness of quantum mechanical description. Bell's work demonstrated that no local hidden-variable theory could account for all quantum mechanical predictions. After that, the experimental verification of Bell's inequality has evolved through several stages.

Freedman and Clauser's experiment in 1972 [3] provided the first experimental evidence supporting quantum mechanics over local hidden-variable theories. Aspect et al. in the early 1980s [4–6] addressed the locality loophole, through time-varying analyzers that changed orientation during the photon's flight, and ensuring spacelike separation between measurements.

Zeilinger et al. fully enforced for the first time the condition of locality [7], and later extended the work over 144 kilometers [8], establishing the persistence of quantum correlations over macroscopic distances.

Other experiments closed the detection loophole [9, 10], which could be exploited to build a local hidden-variable model, and all the loopholes were simultaneously closed by Hensen et al. [11], Giustina et al. [12], and Shalm et al. [13].

A local hidden-variable model is presented, where the measurement process of non-maximally entangled pairs of photons is modeled with a scoring system, combined with a sigmoid-based threshold mechanism. The model leads to violation of Bell's inequality, providing quantum correlations of relative polarizers' angles with a RMSE ≈ 0.01 - 0.14 for the tested configurations, with respect to quantum mechanical predictions.

II. Related Work

The development of local hidden-variable (LHV) models has been a central theme in the foundations of quantum mechanics since Bell's theorem. Over time, Bell nonlocality has evolved from a purely foundational question into a practical resource for quantum information protocols. Understanding the limits of LHV models remains essential for characterizing this resource and for advancing device-independent quantum technologies.

As noted by Hirsch et. al. [14], entanglement and non-

locality are fundamentally different, and do not constitute two sides of the same coin. There are entangled states which cannot produce nonlocal behavior, considering arbitrary (nonsequential) measurements. The correlations of such states can be reproduced using local hidden variable (LHV) models.

A foundational result in the field was provided by Werner [15], who noted that a state of a composite quantum system is classically correlated if it can be approximated by convex combinations of product states, and Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen correlated otherwise. Classically correlated states can be modeled by a hidden-variable theory and satisfy all generalized Bell's inequalities.

Barrett [16] subsequently extended Werner's construction, demonstrating that local hidden-variable descriptions remain valid for certain entangled Werner states even for generalized measurements. However, this broader applicability came at the cost of a reduced parameter range where the model remains effective.

Acín et al. [17] exploited the connection between Bell correlation inequalities and Grothendieck's constant to prove the existence of LHV models for several noisy entangled states. For two-qubit Werner states, they proved that local hidden variable models exist up to a significantly higher noise threshold than Werner's original bound, substantially narrowing the gap to the known Bell violation region. For planar projective measurements, they showed that CHSH inequality violation completely characterizes the nonlocality of two-qubit Werner states.

Tóth and Acín [18] presented a family of three-qubit quantum states with a basic local hidden-variable model, showing that some of those states are genuine and distillable three-partite entangled. These results demonstrated that three-qubit entanglement is not sufficient for a state to be nonlocal.

Almeida et al. [19] investigated the nonlocal properties of states resulting from the mixture of an arbitrary entangled state ρ of two d -dimensional systems and completely depolarized noise, providing bounds on the resistance to noise of the nonlocal correlations. For projective measurements, they showed that the critical value of the noise parameter p for which the state becomes local is at least asymptotically $\log d$ larger than the critical value

for separability.

A significant advancement in understanding what resources are required to construct a LHV model was achieved by Bowles et al. [20], who demonstrated that essentially all entangled states admitting LHV models can be simulated using finite shared randomness, showing a model that simulates noisy two-qubit Werner states using $\log_2(12) \approx 3.58$ bits of shared randomness.

Hirsch et al. [14] presented a method for constructing LHV models applicable to arbitrary entangled states. This method was applied considering general positive-operator-valued measures (POVMs) on the two-qubit Werner state.

De Zela [21] presented a local-realistic model that reproduces quantum predictions concerning Bell tests, claiming that local-realism is fully compatible with correlations that are not of the Bell type. This work used a statistical framework for evaluating relationships between vectors, using inner-product-type correlations.

Marquardt and von Selzam [22] developed a machine learning approach to discover LHV models. They used gradient-descent algorithms to find LHV models that reproduce the statistics of arbitrary measurements for quantum many-body states, providing actual estimates for critical noise levels at which two-qubit Werner states and three-qubit GHZ and W states become nonlocal.

Although existing LHV models have provided valuable insights into the classical simulation of quantum correlations, several approaches rely on idealized assumptions or are limited in their ability to account for realistic features such as detector inefficiencies and finite-resolution effects. This highlights the need for more refined models that can bridge the gap between theoretical constructs and experimental implementations.

The present work introduces a local hidden-variable model that includes a sigmoid-based threshold mechanism, simulating realistic photodetector behavior and exploiting the detection loophole, originally introduced by Pearle [23]. This approach achieves both high detection efficiency and statistically significant violation of Bell's inequality, while preserving locality and violating the fair sampling assumption.

The model explores how classical systems can simulate quantum correlations through a threshold selection mechanism, both for maximally and non-maximally entangled states, offering insight into the classical-quantum boundary under realistic experimental conditions.

III. Theoretical Framework

A source of entangled photons is considered in one of the non-maximally entangled Bell states \mathcal{B} :

$$|\Phi_r\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+r^2}}(|HH\rangle + r|VV\rangle) \quad (1)$$

$$|\Psi_r\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+r^2}}(|HV\rangle + r|VH\rangle) \quad (2)$$

where H and V denote horizontal and vertical polarization states respectively, and r is the entanglement pa-

rameter. For $r = \pm 1$, quantum states are maximally entangled. Hence:

$$|\Phi_r\rangle = \begin{cases} |\Phi_r^+\rangle, & \text{if } r > 0 \\ |\Phi_r^-\rangle, & \text{if } r < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$|\Psi_r\rangle = \begin{cases} |\Psi_r^+\rangle, & \text{if } r > 0 \\ |\Psi_r^-\rangle, & \text{if } r < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Polarization measurements are performed on spacelike separated entangled photons. In the xy plane, where x corresponds to $|H\rangle$ and y to $|V\rangle$, the measurement basis at angle ϕ is:

$$|\phi\rangle = \cos(\phi)|H\rangle + \sin(\phi)|V\rangle \quad (5)$$

$$|\phi^\perp\rangle = -\sin(\phi)|H\rangle + \cos(\phi)|V\rangle \quad (6)$$

The quantum correlations for $|\Phi_r\rangle$ and $|\Psi_r\rangle$ predicted by quantum mechanics are:

$$E_{\Phi_r}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, r) = \cos(2\hat{\alpha})\cos(2\hat{\beta}) + \frac{2r}{1+r^2}\sin(2\hat{\alpha})\sin(2\hat{\beta}) \quad (7)$$

$$E_{\Psi_r}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}, r) = -\cos(2\hat{\alpha})\cos(2\hat{\beta}) + \frac{2r}{1+r^2}\sin(2\hat{\alpha})\sin(2\hat{\beta}) \quad (8)$$

where $\hat{\alpha} \in \{a, a'\}$ and $\hat{\beta} \in \{b, b'\}$ are the orientations of the polarizers in the xy plane, for the first and second photon respectively. The state of the first photon $\lambda_1 = (\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n)$ is randomly drawn from a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\theta, \sigma_G^2)$ with mean θ and standard deviation $\sigma_G = |(1-r^2)|/(\sqrt{3}(1+r^2))$, and that of the second photon λ_2 is defined as:

$$\lambda_2 = \begin{cases} \lambda_1, & \text{if } \mathcal{B} = |\Phi_r^+\rangle \\ -\lambda_1, & \text{if } \mathcal{B} = |\Phi_r^-\rangle \\ -\lambda_1 - \pi/2, & \text{if } \mathcal{B} = |\Psi_r^+\rangle \\ \lambda_1 + \pi/2, & \text{if } \mathcal{B} = |\Psi_r^-\rangle \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The polarization angle θ is randomly drawn from a uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(0, \pi)$, with a probability density function $p(x) = 1/\pi$ if $x \in [0, \pi)$, and 0 elsewhere.

Given the orientations of the polarizers $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$, the cumulative measurement scores (c_1^+, c_1^-) and (c_2^+, c_2^-) are calculated for the first and the second photon respectively as:

$$c_1^+ = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{H} \left(\frac{1 + \sigma_{\mathcal{B}} E_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_1(i), r)}{2} - u_i \right) \times \\ \times \left[w_a(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, r) \cos^2(\hat{\alpha} - \text{s\grave{g}n}(r)\lambda_1^{(i)}) + \right. \\ \left. w_b(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, r) \sin^2(\hat{\alpha} - \text{s\grave{g}n}(r)\lambda_1^{(i)}) \right] \quad (10)$$

$$c_1^- = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{H} \left(\frac{1 - \sigma_{\mathcal{B}} E_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, r)}{2} - u_i \right) \times \left[w_c(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, r) \cos^2(\hat{\alpha} - \text{s\hat{g}n}(r)\lambda_1^{(i)}) + w_d(\hat{\alpha}, \lambda_1^{(i)}, r) \sin^2(\hat{\alpha} - \text{s\hat{g}n}(r)\lambda_1^{(i)}) \right] \quad (11)$$

$$c_2^+ = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{H} \left(\frac{1 + \sigma_{\mathcal{B}} E_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r)}{2} - v_i \right) \times \left[w_a(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r) \cos^2(\hat{\beta} - \text{s\hat{g}n}(r)\lambda_2^{(i)}) + w_b(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r) \sin^2(\hat{\beta} - \text{s\hat{g}n}(r)\lambda_2^{(i)}) \right] \quad (12)$$

$$c_2^- = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathcal{H} \left(\frac{1 - \sigma_{\mathcal{B}} E_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r)}{2} - v_i \right) \times \left[w_c(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r) \cos^2(\hat{\beta} - \text{s\hat{g}n}(r)\lambda_2^{(i)}) + w_d(\hat{\beta}, \lambda_2^{(i)}, r) \sin^2(\hat{\beta} - \text{s\hat{g}n}(r)\lambda_2^{(i)}) \right] \quad (13)$$

where $\lambda_1^{(i)}$ and $\lambda_2^{(i)}$ are the i -th components of λ_1 and λ_2 respectively, u_i and v_i are independent random numbers sampled from a uniform distribution $\mathcal{U}(0, 1)$, $\sigma_{\mathcal{B}} = \{1 \text{ if } \mathcal{B} = |\Phi_r\rangle, -1 \text{ if } \mathcal{B} = |\Psi_r\rangle\}$, $\text{s\hat{g}n}(r)$ is the modified sign function and $\hat{\mathcal{H}}$ is the modified Heaviside function defined as:

$$\text{s\hat{g}n}(r) = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } r \geq 0 \\ -1 & \text{if } r < 0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

$$\hat{\mathcal{H}}(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } x \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The weights $w(\rho, \lambda, r)$ in Eqs. 10–13 are defined as:

$$w_a(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{P_{++}(\rho, \lambda, r)}{P_{++}(\rho, \lambda, r) + P_{--}(\rho, \lambda, r)} \quad (16)$$

$$w_b(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{P_{--}(\rho, \lambda, r)}{P_{++}(\rho, \lambda, r) + P_{--}(\rho, \lambda, r)} \quad (17)$$

$$w_c(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{P_{+-}(\rho, \lambda, r)}{P_{+-}(\rho, \lambda, r) + P_{-+}(\rho, \lambda, r)} \quad (18)$$

$$w_d(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{P_{-+}(\rho, \lambda, r)}{P_{+-}(\rho, \lambda, r) + P_{-+}(\rho, \lambda, r)} \quad (19)$$

where P_{ij} indicates the probability of coincidence of events i and j for the state $|\Phi_r\rangle$ or $|\Psi_r\rangle$, but calculated in a local context, with $\rho \in \{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}\}$ and $\lambda \in \{\lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_2^{(i)}\}$.

The probabilities of coincidence for the state $|\Phi_r\rangle$ are defined as:

$$P_{++}(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{1}{1+r^2} (\cos(\rho) \cos(\lambda) + r \sin(\rho) \sin(\lambda))^2 \quad (20)$$

$$P_{--}(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{1}{1+r^2} (\sin(\rho) \sin(\lambda) + r \cos(\rho) \cos(\lambda))^2 \quad (21)$$

$$P_{+-}(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{1}{1+r^2} (-\cos(\rho) \sin(\lambda) + r \sin(\rho) \cos(\lambda))^2 \quad (22)$$

$$P_{-+}(\rho, \lambda, r) = \frac{1}{1+r^2} (\sin(\rho) \cos(\lambda) - r \cos(\rho) \sin(\lambda))^2 \quad (23)$$

The quantum correlations $E_{\mathcal{B}}(\rho, \lambda, r)$ in Eqs. 10–13 are calculated in a local context, with $\rho \in \{\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}\}$ and $\lambda \in \{\lambda_1^{(i)}, \lambda_2^{(i)}\}$, effectively introducing a form of post-selection that violates the fair sampling assumption.

The detection probabilities $P_{\lambda_i}^+$ and $P_{\lambda_i}^-$ for the '+' and '-' channel respectively are defined with sigmoid functions:

$$P_{\lambda_i}^+ = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-s(\Delta\hat{c}_i - t(r))}} \quad (24)$$

$$P_{\lambda_i}^- = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-s(-\Delta\hat{c}_i - t(r))}} \quad (25)$$

where s is the steepness, $\Delta\hat{c}_1 = (\hat{c}_1^+ - \hat{c}_1^-)$ and $\Delta\hat{c}_2 = \sigma_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{c}_2^+ - \hat{c}_2^-)$ are the net scores of photons 1 and 2 respectively, \hat{c}_1^+ and \hat{c}_1^- are the normalized cumulative scores:

$$\hat{c}_1^+ = \frac{c_1^+}{c_1^+ + c_1^-} \quad \hat{c}_1^- = \frac{c_1^-}{c_1^+ + c_1^-} \quad (26)$$

$$\hat{c}_2^+ = \frac{c_2^+}{c_2^+ + c_2^-} \quad \hat{c}_2^- = \frac{c_2^-}{c_2^+ + c_2^-} \quad (27)$$

and $t(r)$ is the threshold function defined as:

$$t(r) = \frac{\tau_0 + \tau_1 r^2 + \tau_2 r^4}{1 + \tau_3 r^2 + \tau_4 r^4} \quad (28)$$

For the state $|\Psi_r\rangle$, the same expressions in Eqs. 20–23 are used, since the anti-correlation is implemented through sign swapping of the second photon's net score.

For each photon λ_i , random numbers $\hat{u}_i, \hat{v}_i \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 1)$ are drawn to determine the measurement outcome:

$$d_{\lambda_i} = \begin{cases} +1 & \text{if } P_{\lambda_i}^+ > \hat{u}_i \text{ and } P_{\lambda_i}^- \leq \hat{v}_i \\ -1 & \text{if } P_{\lambda_i}^+ \leq \hat{u}_i \text{ and } P_{\lambda_i}^- > \hat{v}_i \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

where $d_{\lambda_i} = +1$ indicates detection in the “+” channel, $d_{\lambda_i} = -1$ indicates detection in the “-” channel, and $d_{\lambda_i} = 0$ indicates no detection, while \hat{u}_i and \hat{v}_i model the quantum noise floor resulting from thermal fluctuations, shot noise, and electronic noise.

Coincidences are recorded by comparing the detection outcomes. The single detection efficiencies η are determined by the mechanism described above. The correlation function $E_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta})$ for polarizer orientations $\hat{\alpha}$ and $\hat{\beta}$ is calculated from the coincidence statistics:

$$E_{\mathcal{B}}(\hat{\alpha}, \hat{\beta}) = \frac{N_{++} + N_{--} - N_{+-} - N_{-+}}{N_{++} + N_{--} + N_{+-} + N_{-+}} \quad (30)$$

where N_{ij} represents the number of coincidences with outcome i at the first analyzer and j at the second analyzer. The value of the Bell parameter function S is calculated using the CHSH inequality [24]:

$$S = E_{\mathcal{B}}(a, b) - E_{\mathcal{B}}(a, b') + E_{\mathcal{B}}(a', b) + E_{\mathcal{B}}(a', b') \quad (31)$$

IV. Threshold Calibration

The coefficients of the threshold function $t(r)$ in Eq. 28 were determined using a leave-one-out cross-validation procedure, designed to ensure generalization across different polarizers’ configurations.

For $r \in \{0.0, 0.1, 0.2, \dots, 3.0\}$, fifteen independent optimization iterations were performed, each employing seven randomly generated polarizer configurations with angles uniformly sampled from $[0, \pi]$.

Within each iteration, seven-fold leave-one-out cross-validation was applied: six configurations served as the training set for threshold optimization while the seventh was reserved for independent validation. This process cycled through all possible train/test partitions, yielding 105 independent threshold estimates per r value.

The optimization procedure used grid search over threshold range $[0.001, 0.800]$ with 40 equally-spaced evaluation points to minimize the multi-objective function:

$$\begin{aligned} F(t') &= |\eta_1(t') - \eta_0| + |\eta_2(t') - \eta_0| \\ &\quad + p_1 \cdot \max(0, |\eta_1(t') - \eta_2(t')| - p_2) \\ &\quad + p_3 \cdot |S(t') - S_q| \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

where $\eta_1(t')$ and $\eta_2(t')$ represent detection efficiencies of detectors 1 and 2 at threshold t' , $\eta_0 = 0.84$ is the target efficiency chosen such that the Bell parameter S approaches $2\sqrt{2}$ for the polarizers’ configuration that maximizes the Tsirelson bound when $r = 1$, $S(t')$ and S_q are respectively the measured and the quantum mechanical prediction of S , given r and the considered polarizers’ configuration.

The multi-objective function optimizes three objectives: $|\eta_1(t') - \eta_0|$ and $|\eta_2(t') - \eta_0|$ constrain both detector efficiencies to the target value η_0 , $p_3 \cdot |S(t') - S_q|$

keeps the Bell parameter S close to quantum mechanical predictions, and $p_1 \cdot \max(0, |\eta_1(t') - \eta_2(t')| - p_2)$ prevents large detection efficiency imbalances between detectors. The regularization parameters were set to $p_1 = 2.0$, $p_2 = 0.024$, and $p_3 = 0.1$.

For each threshold evaluation, the multi-objective function was estimated through Monte Carlo simulation of 2000 entangled photon pairs per configuration, averaged over three independent runs for statistical stability. Each photon pair was subjected to linear polarization measurements at randomly selected angle combinations from the current configuration set, with detection outcomes determined using the mechanism described above, including hidden variables λ_1 and λ_2 with $n = 21$ components.

Cross-validation yielded 15 successful iterations for all r values. Threshold standard deviations across validation folds were $\sigma_t = 0.0049 \pm 0.0030$. Detection efficiencies on held-out configurations achieved $\eta_1 = 0.841 \pm 0.003$ and $\eta_2 = 0.841 \pm 0.004$ across the parameter range, with detector imbalance $|\eta_1 - \eta_2| = 0.002 \pm 0.002$.

The cross-validated threshold reaches maximum values near $r = 1$ corresponding to maximally entangled Bell states. Fitting to Eq. 28 yielded optimal parameters $\tau_0 = 0.077$, $\tau_1 = 0.388$, $\tau_2 = 0.049$, $\tau_3 = 0.203$, and $\tau_4 = 0.838$, with RMSE = 0.0039 and $R^2 = 0.994$.

The empirical determination of the parameters serves as a detector characterization procedure, where the fitted values model measurable physical quantities such as threshold sensitivity, saturation behavior, and noise characteristics that would be obtained during experimental calibration of the detection apparatus.

V. Model’s Parameters

The Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{N}(\theta, \sigma_G^2)$ used to generate λ_1 and λ_2 reflects the central limit theorem applied to multiple independent physical fluctuations in photon generation and propagation, representing the maximum entropy distribution given variance constraints.

The sample size n represents the number of independent photon interaction events processed by each detector before making a measurement decision. It models the multi-dimensional character of photon polarization states under measurement, where each component represents a distinct degree of freedom that contributes to the final detection outcome.

Real photodetectors integrate signal over finite time windows, during which multiple photon interactions contribute to the final detection outcome. The choice of n must provide sufficient statistical sampling to distinguish between signal and background noise, capturing the statistical fluctuations necessary for quantum correlation reproduction.

The Gaussian standard deviation $\sigma_G(r) = |1 - r^2|/(\sqrt{3}(1 + r^2))$ models the physical expectation that measurement uncertainty decreases with entanglement strength, reaching zero uncertainty for maximally entangled states.

The asymmetry of the non-maximally entangled states ϕ_r and ψ_r is quantified by $|1 - r^2|/(1 + r^2)$, which measures the difference between the probabilities of the two components in their respective superpositions.

The factor $1/\sqrt{3}$ ensures that the hidden variable distribution $\mathcal{N}(\theta, \sigma_G^2)$ produces the same statistical dispersion as uniform noise with probability difference $|1 - r^2|/(1 + r^2)$, since $\text{Var}[\mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)] = \text{Var}[\mathcal{U}(-a, a)]$ when $\sigma = a/\sqrt{3}$.

The score weights $w(\rho, \lambda, r)$ model how detection probability varies with the overlap between the hidden variable state λ and the polarizer's orientation ρ . The weighted angular dependence $w_a \cos^2(\alpha - \lambda) + w_b \sin^2(\alpha - \lambda)$ represents the decomposition of the photon's polarization response along two orthogonal detector axes.

The terms $w_a \cos^2(\alpha - \lambda)$ and $w_b \sin^2(\alpha - \lambda)$ capture the projection components along perpendicular directions, with weights w_a and w_b (derived from local coincidence probabilities) modulating the relative sensitivity of each polarization component.

This mechanism models how avalanche photodiodes and photomultiplier tubes exhibit orientation-dependent quantum efficiency, accumulating multiple photon interactions with polarization-dependent gain before triggering detection events.

The sigmoid steepness s characterizes detector response sharpness, analogous to gain parameters in photodetection systems. High values model high-resolution detectors with sharp threshold/detection transitions.

The function $t(r)$ represents how detection threshold varies with entanglement strength, where its rational form exhibits a symmetric double-peaked structure, with maxima occurring when $r \approx \pm 1$. It provides appropriate asymptotic behavior for large $|r|$, ensuring bounded threshold values that prevent numerical instabilities in the sigmoid detection mechanism. The threshold response captures the physical expectation that maximally entangled states require the higher detection thresholds to discriminate quantum correlations from noise.

For $|r| \ll 1$, $t(r)$ exhibits approximately quadratic growth from the baseline value τ_0 :

$$t(r) \approx \tau_0 + (\tau_1 - \tau_0\tau_3)r^2 + \mathcal{O}(r^4) \quad (33)$$

The base threshold τ_0 corresponds to the detection probability in the absence of quantum correlations, assuming a symmetric response function centered at this value. It represents the detector's intrinsic sensitivity floor, determined by dark current, thermal noise, and background effects that limit signal discrimination at zero entanglement.

For $|r| \approx 1$, the threshold reaches its peaks, corresponding to optimal detection conditions where the signal-to-noise is maximized for quantum correlation detection.

For $|r| \gg 1$, the threshold approaches the asymptotic value τ_2/τ_4 , modeling physical detector characteristics, where beyond optimal entanglement further increases of $|r|$ do not significantly improve detection efficiency.

The detection mechanism models realistic polarization-sensitive photodetectors. The sigmoid-based detection probabilities $P_{\lambda_i}^+$ and $P_{\lambda_i}^-$ reflect the competitive nature of orthogonal polarization measurements, where $\Delta\hat{c}_1 = (\hat{c}_1^+ - \hat{c}_1^-)$ and $\Delta\hat{c}_2 = \sigma_B(\hat{c}_2^+ - \hat{c}_2^-)$ represent the local channel discrimination signals for photons 1 and 2 respectively.

VI. Simulation Setup

In the first setup the source that generates photon pairs in the non-maximally entangled Bell state is $|\Phi_r\rangle$ (maximally entangled for $r = \pm 1$). The configuration used is $\alpha = (0^\circ, 45^\circ)$, $\beta = (22.5^\circ, 67.5^\circ)$, $n = 21$, $s = 20$, $\tau_0 = 0.077$, $\tau_1 = 0.388$, $\tau_2 = 0.049$, $\tau_3 = 0.203$, and $\tau_4 = 0.838$. Relevant metrics include S and its statistical significance (for the state and configuration that maximizes the Tsirelson bound), across 100 independent simulations with 10000 pairs of entangled photons generated for each simulation, and its standard error; the single detection efficiencies η_1 and η_2 with their standard errors; the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) between the model's correlations $\hat{E}_{\Phi_r^\pm}$ and those predicted by quantum mechanics $E_{\Phi_r^\pm}$ for the polarizers' orientations, using 100 independent simulations with 10000 pairs of entangled photons generated for each simulation, and its standard error.

In the second setup the source that generates photon pairs in the non-maximally entangled Bell state is $|\Psi_r\rangle$ (maximally entangled for $r = \pm 1$). The configuration used is $\alpha = (94.4^\circ, 62.4^\circ)$, $\beta = (-6.5^\circ, 25.5^\circ)$, $n = 21$, $s = 20$, $\tau_0 = 0.077$, $\tau_1 = 0.388$, $\tau_2 = 0.049$, $\tau_3 = 0.203$, and $\tau_4 = 0.838$. Relevant metrics include S and its standard error; the single detection efficiencies η_1 and η_2 with their standard errors; the RMSE between the model's correlations $\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^\pm}$ and those predicted by quantum mechanics $E_{\Psi_r^\pm}$ for the polarizers' orientations, and its standard error, as in the first setup.

The Mersenne Twister algorithm is used for all random number generation (i.e., angle selection, cumulative scoring and detection mechanisms), ensuring a long period ($2^{19937} - 1$) and high-quality statistical properties.

VII. Results and Discussion

Tables I-IV present the simulation results for the entangled states and configurations.

For the $|\Phi_r^+\rangle$ state (Table I) with polarizer settings $\alpha = (0^\circ, 45^\circ)$ and $\beta = (22.5^\circ, 67.5^\circ)$, the Bell parameter S increases with r from 1.5602 ± 0.0042 at $r = 0.1$ to a maximum of 2.8179 ± 0.0034 at $r = 1.0$. The S value achieved at $r = 1.0$ corresponds to a statistical significance of approximately 27σ .

For the $|\Phi_r^-\rangle$ state (Table II) with polarizer settings $\alpha = (0^\circ, 45^\circ)$ and $\beta = (22.5^\circ, 67.5^\circ)$, the Bell parameter S decreases with increasing $|r|$, from 1.4502 ± 0.0041 at $r = -0.1$ to 0.0015 ± 0.0030 at $r = -1.0$.

For the $|\Psi_r^+\rangle$ state (Table III) with polarizer settings $\alpha = (94.4^\circ, 62.4^\circ)$ and $\beta = (-6.5^\circ, 25.5^\circ)$, the Bell parameter S ranges from 1.4491 ± 0.0031 at $r = 0.1$ to 1.8276 ± 0.0033 at $r = 1.0$.

TABLE I. Bell parameter S , single detection efficiencies η_1 and η_2 , RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Phi_r^+}, E_{\Phi_r^+}$), $\alpha = (0^\circ, 45^\circ)$, $\beta = (22.5^\circ, 67.5^\circ)$, $r > 0$.

r	Bell S	η_1 (%)	η_2 (%)	RMSE
0.1	1.5602 ± 0.0042	82.63 ± 0.04	87.64 ± 0.03	0.0862 ± 0.0012
0.2	1.6503 ± 0.0041	82.20 ± 0.04	85.30 ± 0.04	0.1243 ± 0.0011
0.3	1.9402 ± 0.0038	82.14 ± 0.04	83.20 ± 0.04	0.0890 ± 0.0011
0.4	2.2819 ± 0.0036	83.11 ± 0.03	83.03 ± 0.04	0.0353 ± 0.0010
0.5	2.5295 ± 0.0034	83.99 ± 0.04	83.86 ± 0.04	0.0175 ± 0.0007
0.6	2.6567 ± 0.0032	84.18 ± 0.04	84.19 ± 0.04	0.0175 ± 0.0006
0.7	2.7308 ± 0.0034	84.23 ± 0.04	84.24 ± 0.03	0.0179 ± 0.0006
0.8	2.7777 ± 0.0035	84.24 ± 0.03	84.21 ± 0.04	0.0164 ± 0.0006
0.9	2.8077 ± 0.0035	84.27 ± 0.04	84.17 ± 0.04	0.0166 ± 0.0006
1.0	2.8179 ± 0.0034	84.09 ± 0.04	84.12 ± 0.03	0.0154 ± 0.0006

For the $|\Psi_r^-\rangle$ state (Table IV) with polarizer settings $\alpha = (94.4^\circ, 62.4^\circ)$ and $\beta = (-6.5^\circ, 25.5^\circ)$, the Bell parameter S ranges from 1.2804 ± 0.0033 at $r = -0.1$ to 0.6687 ± 0.0029 at $r = -1.0$.

TABLE II. Bell parameter S , single detection efficiencies η_1 and η_2 , RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^-}, E_{\Psi_r^-}$), $\alpha = (0^\circ, 45^\circ)$, $\beta = (22.5^\circ, 67.5^\circ)$, $r < 0$.

r	Bell S	η_1 (%)	η_2 (%)	RMSE
-0.1	1.4502 ± 0.0041	82.75 ± 0.03	87.57 ± 0.03	0.0882 ± 0.0012
-0.2	1.2566 ± 0.0045	82.24 ± 0.03	85.37 ± 0.03	0.1242 ± 0.0013
-0.3	0.8785 ± 0.0041	82.20 ± 0.04	83.21 ± 0.04	0.0903 ± 0.0012
-0.4	0.5135 ± 0.0043	83.08 ± 0.04	83.01 ± 0.04	0.0367 ± 0.0010
-0.5	0.2655 ± 0.0039	83.93 ± 0.04	83.86 ± 0.04	0.0182 ± 0.0007
-0.6	0.1495 ± 0.0034	84.28 ± 0.03	84.14 ± 0.04	0.0169 ± 0.0005
-0.7	0.0729 ± 0.0034	84.19 ± 0.04	84.16 ± 0.04	0.0162 ± 0.0006
-0.8	0.0300 ± 0.0036	84.22 ± 0.03	84.23 ± 0.04	0.0166 ± 0.0007
-0.9	0.0107 ± 0.0032	84.19 ± 0.04	84.18 ± 0.04	0.0168 ± 0.0006
-1.0	0.0015 ± 0.0030	84.18 ± 0.04	84.20 ± 0.04	0.0152 ± 0.0005

Tables V and IV report RMSE values between the model's correlations $\hat{E}_{\Phi_r^\pm}$ (or $\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^\pm}$) and those predicted by quantum mechanics $E_{\Phi_r^\pm}$ (or $E_{\Psi_r^\pm}$), for different entanglement parameter r , calculated by sampling the relative angle $\delta\theta$ at intervals of 10° , across the range $[-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$, using 100 independent simulations with 10000 pairs of entangled photons generated for each simulation.

The RMSE between the model's correlations and quantum mechanical predictions ranges approximately from 0.14 at $|r| = 0.1$ to 0.01 at $|r| = 1.0$. The model exhibits increasing performance with increasing values of the entanglement parameter r , with respect to both the predicted quantum correlations and the coincidence percentages.

For the $|\Phi_r^+\rangle$ state, the Bell parameter of $S = 2.8179 \pm 0.0034$ at $r = 1.0$ is achieved with a joint detection efficiency of $\eta = 69.26\% \pm 0.04\%$, hence $\eta \cdot S/2 \approx 0.9758 \pm 0.0013$, indicating that the model operates close to the theoretical efficiency bound for Bell's inequality violation in local hidden-variable theories.

VIII. Conclusions

The present work introduces a sigmoid-based threshold mechanism that models linear polarization measurements of entangled photons and photodetector responses. This approach models the measurement process both for maximally and non-maximally entangled states, using a scor-

TABLE III. Bell parameter S , single detection efficiencies η_1 and η_2 , RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^+}, E_{\Psi_r^+}$), $\alpha = (94.4^\circ, 62.4^\circ)$, $\beta = (-6.5^\circ, 25.5^\circ)$, $r > 0$.

r	Bell S	η_1 (%)	η_2 (%)	RMSE
0.1	1.4491 ± 0.0031	87.75 ± 0.03	88.08 ± 0.03	0.1396 ± 0.0008
0.2	1.4762 ± 0.0034	86.07 ± 0.04	86.27 ± 0.04	0.1062 ± 0.0007
0.3	1.5923 ± 0.0036	85.10 ± 0.04	85.20 ± 0.03	0.0868 ± 0.0007
0.4	1.7126 ± 0.0031	85.20 ± 0.04	85.25 ± 0.04	0.0602 ± 0.0005
0.5	1.7683 ± 0.0029	85.38 ± 0.04	85.22 ± 0.03	0.0391 ± 0.0005
0.6	1.7947 ± 0.0031	85.20 ± 0.04	84.75 ± 0.04	0.0256 ± 0.0007
0.7	1.8025 ± 0.0035	85.12 ± 0.04	84.35 ± 0.03	0.0197 ± 0.0007
0.8	1.8164 ± 0.0034	85.22 ± 0.03	84.60 ± 0.03	0.0198 ± 0.0006
0.9	1.8387 ± 0.0035	84.95 ± 0.03	85.15 ± 0.04	0.0278 ± 0.0008
1.0	1.8276 ± 0.0033	84.12 ± 0.04	84.15 ± 0.04	0.0216 ± 0.0008

TABLE IV. Bell parameter S , single detection efficiencies η_1 and η_2 , RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^-}, E_{\Psi_r^-}$), $\alpha = (94.4^\circ, 62.4^\circ)$, $\beta = (-6.5^\circ, 25.5^\circ)$, $r < 0$.

r	Bell S	η_1 (%)	η_2 (%)	RMSE
-0.1	1.2804 ± 0.0033	87.79 ± 0.04	88.12 ± 0.03	0.1611 ± 0.0010
-0.2	1.1013 ± 0.0037	86.06 ± 0.04	86.28 ± 0.04	0.1349 ± 0.0009
-0.3	0.9494 ± 0.0032	85.13 ± 0.03	85.22 ± 0.04	0.0938 ± 0.0009
-0.4	0.8540 ± 0.0030	85.17 ± 0.03	85.21 ± 0.03	0.0535 ± 0.0008
-0.5	0.7734 ± 0.0034	85.43 ± 0.04	85.18 ± 0.03	0.0316 ± 0.0009
-0.6	0.7199 ± 0.0036	85.19 ± 0.04	84.81 ± 0.04	0.0292 ± 0.0008
-0.7	0.7113 ± 0.0033	85.12 ± 0.03	84.41 ± 0.03	0.0331 ± 0.0009
-0.8	0.7570 ± 0.0035	85.26 ± 0.04	84.48 ± 0.04	0.0569 ± 0.0012
-0.9	0.7923 ± 0.0035	85.02 ± 0.04	85.17 ± 0.03	0.0705 ± 0.0013
-1.0	0.6687 ± 0.0029	84.09 ± 0.04	84.13 ± 0.04	0.0151 ± 0.0006

TABLE V. RMSE of the model's correlations ($\hat{E}_{\Phi_r^\pm}$) and quantum mechanical correlations ($E_{\Phi_r^\pm}$).

r	RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Phi_r^+}, E_{\Phi_r^+}$)	r	RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Phi_r^-}, E_{\Phi_r^-}$)
0.1	0.138738 ± 0.000200	-0.1	0.138895 ± 0.000172
0.2	0.118140 ± 0.000166	-0.2	0.117823 ± 0.000185
0.3	0.084469 ± 0.000169	-0.3	0.084262 ± 0.000143
0.4	0.048392 ± 0.000127	-0.4	0.048285 ± 0.000111
0.5	0.028026 ± 0.000096	-0.5	0.028031 ± 0.000096
0.6	0.018411 ± 0.000119	-0.6	0.018173 ± 0.000108
0.7	0.014329 ± 0.000131	-0.7	0.014438 ± 0.000157
0.8	0.013566 ± 0.000161	-0.8	0.014034 ± 0.000190
0.9	0.013958 ± 0.000189	-0.9	0.013791 ± 0.000176
1.0	0.013801 ± 0.000219	-1.0	0.013785 ± 0.000219

TABLE VI. RMSE of the model's correlations $\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^\pm}$ and quantum mechanical correlations $E_{\Psi_r^\pm}$

r	RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^+}, E_{\Psi_r^+}$)	r	RMSE($\hat{E}_{\Psi_r^-}, E_{\Psi_r^-}$)
0.1	0.124210 ± 0.000179	-0.1	0.124759 ± 0.000178
0.2	0.115772 ± 0.000165	-0.2	0.115274 ± 0.000183
0.3	0.093687 ± 0.000180	-0.3	0.093549 ± 0.000156
0.4	0.059090 ± 0.000155	-0.4	0.058853 ± 0.000157
0.5	0.039273 ± 0.000169	-0.5	0.039307 ± 0.000173
0.6	0.034254 ± 0.000216	-0.6	0.034712 ± 0.000204
0.7	0.035626 ± 0.000228	-0.7	0.035249 ± 0.000253
0.8	0.027525 ± 0.000277	-0.8	0.027384 ± 0.000263
0.9	0.017990 ± 0.000227	-0.9	0.018066 ± 0.000193
1.0	0.013734 ± 0.000220	-1.0	0.013716 ± 0.000220

ing mechanism that produces quantum-like correlations, while maintaining locality. The numerical simulations demonstrate that this mechanism produces correlations that violate Bell's inequality with statistical significance and high detection efficiency, providing insights into the classical-quantum boundary. The model produces correlations with RMSE ≈ 0.01 - 0.14 and single detection efficiencies $\eta_{1,2} \approx 84\% - 88\%$. The results indicate that the sigmoid-based model can approximate quantum cor-

relations through an emergent mechanism based on the violation of the fair sampling assumption. The model's features provide a confirmation of the fundamental constraints that any local hidden-variable model must satisfy to approximate quantum mechanical theoretical correlations. Future work includes exploring further mechanisms to model the interaction of the photon with the measurement apparatus.

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